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Review Article

Documentation of Liquid Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (LC-MS) Technique for Quantitative Analysis of Naproxen in Human Plasma

Iram Rashid Gore*, Swati Wakchoure¹, Dhanashree Kathole, Dev Gaikwad, Nishita Hole

Shivajirao S. Jondhle College of Pharmacy, Asangaon, Thane, Mumbai, Maharashtra, India a.

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ABSTRACT

Naproxen is a commonly used non steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID) employed in treatment of pain, fever and inflammation. It has the ability to bind and inhibit synthesis of prostaglandins and produces anti inflammatory effect. Accurate quantification of naproxen in human plasma is essential for bioavailability, pharmacokinetic and clinical studies. Liquid chromatography -Mass Spectrometry has emerged as a gold standard analytical approach for such purpose due to its good sensitivity, specificity and rapid analysis. A quick and selective LC-MS approach for quantification of naproxen in human plasma can be used in therapeutic drug monitoring as well as in its bioequivalence study. This review article highlights instrumentation, process and methodology employed in quantitative analysis of naproxen in human plasma using LC-MS. Factors such as sample preparation technique (for example, protein precipitation, liquid-liquid extraction and solid-phase extraction), chromatographic conditions, mass spectrometric parameters and method validation are critically important.

INTRODUCTION

Naproxen (+)-2-(6-methoxy-2-naphthyl) propionic acid is a non steroidal anti-inflammatory drug with anti-inflammatory, analgesic and antipyretic properties that is typically favored over acetylsalicylic acid (aspirin) due to greater absorption by oral administration and fewer side effects [1]. Anti-inflammatory effect of naproxen

are generally assumed to be related to the inhibition of cyclooxygenase and consequent decrease in prostaglandin concentration in various fluids. [2]. Majority of its therapeutic efficacy is most likely accomplished by prostaglandin synthesis inhibition [3]. It is commonly prescribed for managing pain, inflammation and fever caused by range of illnesses. It is available in both

*Corresponding Author: Iram Rashid Gore

Address: Shivajirao S. Jondhle College of Pharmacy, Asangaon, Thane, Mumbai, Maharashtra, India.

Email : eramgore3@gmail.com

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prescription and over-the-counter (OTC) forms. Naproxen is mildly soluble in water but more soluble in organic solvents like ethanol and methanol. It is acidic in nature, and has its pKa of around 4.15 permits it to be ionized at physiological pH, influencing its pharmacokinetics and absorption [4]

Mechanism of action of Naproxen

Naproxen exerts its effects by suppressing the enzyme cyclooxygenase (COX), specifically the COX-1 and COX-2 isoforms [5]. This inhibition prevents synthesis of prostaglandins, which are lipid molecules involved in pain, inflammation and fever responses.

- COX-1 inhibition: COX-1 is responsible for producing prostaglandins that reserve the stomach lining and support platelet activity. Naproxen's inhibition of COX-1 contributes to gastro intestinal (GI) side effects and significant bleeding concerns.
- COX-2 inhibition: COX-2 is induced during inflammation, and its inhibition reduces inflammation and pain in affected tissues [6].

Naproxen is available in several forms including tablets, liquid suspensions and extended-release formulations. The dosage is determined by the ailment being treated and how the patient responds. To decrease gastro intestinal symptoms, Naproxen should be taken with food or milk [7].

Pharmacokinetics of Naproxen

1. Absorption: Naproxen is quickly absorbed through the gastrointestinal system and reaches maximal plasma concentrations (C_{max}) within 2-4 hours of oral administration.
2. Distribution: it has high plasma protein binding capacity, particularly binding to albumin, which impacts its distribution and half-life.
3. Metabolism: Naproxen undergoes hepatic metabolism primarily through demethylation to form its main metabolite,

desmethylnaproxen. This metabolite is conjugated into glucuronide conjugate.

4. Excretion: Naproxen and its metabolites are primarily eliminated by the kidneys, with a half-life of around 12-17 hours.[8]

Uses of Naproxen

1. Pain relief : Naproxen is used to alleviate mild to moderate pain. It is effective in treating headaches, dental pain, muscle aches and back aches. Because of its relatively extended half-life, it offers sustained pain relief over several hours.
2. Arthritis and inflammatory conditions: Naproxen is frequently prescribed for chronic inflammatory diseases such as Rheumatoid Arthritis, Osteoarthritis, Ankylosing Spondylitis.
3. Gout: Naproxen is effective in managing acute gout attacks, as it reduces the inflammation and pain associated with elevated uric acid level in joints.
4. Dysmenorrhea: For menstrual pain, naproxen is often recommended due to its efficacy in reducing cramps, which are caused by inflammation of the uterine lining.
5. Fever reduction: Like other NSAIDs, naproxen is also used to reduce fever by inhibiting the enzymes responsible for fever production [9].

Side Effects and Risks of Naproxen

Like other NSAIDs, naproxen has a variety of potential side effects, particularly when used for an extended period of time or at high doses. Common adverse effects include gastro intestinal problems such as stomach discomfort, nausea, indigestion, heartburn, headache, dizziness, drowsiness and fatigue [10].

Serious complications while using Naproxen

1. Gastrointestinal bleeding: Naproxen can cause ulceration and bleeding in the stomach or intestines, particularly in older adults are

those with a history of GI disorders and issues.

2. Cardiovascular risks: Naproxen has been associated with increased risk of heart attack or stroke, especially with prolonged use or in patients with pre-existing cardiovascular disorders.
3. Renal impairment: Naproxen may reduce renal blood flow, potentially causing kidney damage in patients with pre-existing kidney disease or those who are dehydrated.
4. Hypersensitivity reactions: Some patients may notice allergic reactions to naproxen, such as rash, hives, or anaphylaxis [11].

Drug Interactions of Naproxen

Naproxen may interact with a variety of medications, resulting in adverse effects or reduced efficacy including:

1. Anticoagulants: Naproxen can increase the risk of bleeding when combined with anticoagulants like Warfarin or anti platelet agents like Aspirin.

2. Anti hypertensive drugs: NSAIDs can reduce the effectiveness of blood pressure medications, particularly ACE inhibitors and diuretics.
3. Methotrexate: Naproxen may increase methotrexate levels, raising the risk of toxicity [12].

Several chromatographic methods have been invented for determination of naproxen in raw material, plasma, urine, intestinal perfusion samples and pharmaceutical preparations. The coupling of HPLC with mass spectrometry is now widely acknowledged as a preferred technique for quantifying small molecule drugs and metabolites in biological matrices. Since this procedure is exceedingly selective and sensitive [7]. LC-MS technique was successfully employed to provide a satisfactory sensitivity and selectivity in a desirable time of chromatographic run [8].

Figure 1. Structure Of Naproxen

Liquid Chromatography -Mass Spectrometry Technique

Liquid chromatography- mass spectrometry LC-MS is an analytical chemistry technique that combines the physical separation capabilities of liquid chromatography or HPLC with the mass analysis capabilities of mass spectrometry [9]. Coupled chromatography systems are common in chemical analysis because the individual capabilities of each technique are enhanced synergistically when combined [10]. While liquid

chromatography separate mixtures with multiple components, mass spectrometry provides spectral information that can be used to identify each separated component [16]. LC-MS is not only sensitive but provides selective detection reducing need for complete chromatographic separation [17]. LC-MS is also ideal for metabolomics due to its broad coverage for a wide range of chemicals [18]. This Tandem approach can be used to investigate biochemical, organic and inorganic compounds often encountered in complex samples

of environmental and biological origin. Hence, LC-MS can be used in variety of industries including biotechnology, environment monitoring, food processing and pharmaceutical agrochemical and cosmetics [19]. In addition to the liquid chromatography and mass spectrometry devices, LC-MS system includes an interface for efficiently transferring the separated component from the LC column into the MS ion source. The interface is required since the LC and MS devices are inherently incompatible. While the mobile phase in a LC system is a pressurized liquid, the MS analyzers typically operate under high vacuum. Therefore, it is not possible to directly pump the eluate from the LC column into the MS source. The interface is a mechanically simple element of the LC-MS system that conveyed the maximum quantity of analyte, remove a significant portion of the mobile phase used in LC and preserves the chemical identity of the chromatography products. The interface should not interfere with the ionizing efficiency and vacuum conditions of the MS system [19].

Instrumentation of Liquid Chromatography - Mass Spectrometry (LC-MS)

LC-MS system consist of a pump, an injector to introduce the sample, a column to separate the analytes and a mass spectrometer detector. Liquid chromatography separates dissolved analytes by utilizing variations in the respective affinity for the solvent or mobile phase and that of stationery phase or column media. Separation can be influenced by changing such variable as column packing material, solvent choice, solvent ratios and pH. Most modern LC systems have at least two different solvents: an organic phase (usually methanol or acetonitrile) and an aqueous buffer at a specific pH. Introduction of the analytes into the MS detector can be achieved through several different systems including electrospray ionization (ESI) and atmospheric pressure chemical ionization (APCI). In most cases the eluent needs

to be removed before ionization and introduction into the mass spectrometer [11].

Applications of LC-MS

LC-MS allows detection of low concentration of naproxen, which is critical in pharmacokinetic investigations. Human plasma contains several components and LC-MS can successfully distinguish naproxen from these interferences. Mass spectrometry can analyze, identify and quantify both naproxen and its metabolites, giving a complete view of drug metabolism. Hence it makes LC-MS preferred choice for analysis of naproxen in clinical and research settings. LC-MS play a crucial role in metabolomics and proteomics as well as identifying proteins in biological systems. The coupling of MS with LC systems is effective because liquid chromatography can separate delicate and complex natural mixtures, whose chemical composition needs to be accurately determined. LC-MS has applications in volatile explosive residue analysis.[20]. Other important applications of LC-MS include the analysis of food, pesticides, and plant phenols [21].

Aim and purpose

1. Pharmacokinetic studies: These studies aim understand how naproxen is absorb, distributed, metabolised and eliminated in the body. This aids in determining dosing schedule and understanding the duration of action.
2. Therapeutic drug monitoring: For patients using naproxen, monitoring plasma level insure the drug remain within therapeutic range, optimizing efficacy and minimizing side effects and toxicity.
3. Bioavailability and bio equivalence studies: In the development of new formulation or generic drug, LC-MS analysis of naproxen in plasma evaluates how much of the drug reaches systemic circulation and compares bioavailability

4. Toxicology and safety study: To detect build up in the plasma which could be associated with toxicity particularly in long-term or high-dose therapy [31].
5. Drug interaction studies: By analyzing plasma level in patients taking multiple medications, researchers can detect interactions that affect naproxen's pharmacokinetics [22].

Why Zidovudine is chosen as standard?

Zidovudine is chosen as benchmark because it has similar physicochemical properties to Naproxen. Zidovudine has similar chromatographic behavior and ionization property in the mass spectrometer. Zidovudine has define retention times and mass spectral fragmentation patterns that can aid in developing sensitive and specific methods for detecting and quantifying naproxen in human plasma. In addition to Zidovudine, several other drugs may be used as standards for analyzing naproxen in human plasma via LC-MS

Ibuprofen: Another non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug that may have similar properties to naproxen.

Diclofenac: A commonly used non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug with distinct pharmacokinetic properties.

Caffeine: Sometimes used due to its well characterized pharmacokinetic and broad clinical relevance.

Warfarin: Used sometimes in pharmacokinetic studies specially in the context of drug interaction research.

Alternative methods for analysis of Naproxen

While liquid chromatography mass spectrometry (LC-MS) is a very sensitive and specific technique for detecting naproxen in human plasma, various alternative methods can be utilized depending on the required sensitivity, specificity and instrumentation availability. Some of the common alternatives are:

1. High performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) with UV detection: This is a widely used alternative for naproxen quantification. Naproxen has high absorbance in the UV range, which makes UV detection effective. However, HPLC -UV may lack the sensitivity and specificity of LC-MS.
2. Gas chromatography-Mass spectrometry (GC-MS): GC-MS can we used for naproxen analysis, however it requires a derivatization step to make naproxen volatile for GC analysis. This method is less commonly used for naproxen because of the additional sample preparation steps required.
3. Capillary Electrophoresis (CE): CE is an alternative method that can separate ionic compounds based on their charge and size. It is relatively fast and requires minimal solvent, making it environmentally friendly. However, it may not offer the same level of sensitivity as LC-MS.
4. Immunoassays: Techniques like enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) can be performed to quantify naproxen. Immunoassays are generally highly specific, but they can exhibit cross- reactivity with structurally related compounds and may lack quantitative precision.
5. Ultra-Performance Liquid Chromatography (UPLC): UPLC is an upgraded variant of HPLC that enables faster analysis with improved resolution and sensitivity. When combined with UV or fluorescence detection, it can serve as an alternative to traditional HPLC-UV, providing increased efficiency.
6. Fluorescence Spectroscopy: This method involve derivatizing naproxen to form a fluorescent molecule, allowing for detection via fluorescence. However, it involves additional chemical processes for derivatization and maybe less specific than LC-MS

7. Electrochemical Detection (ECD): Electrochemical detection can be used with HPLC to detect naproxen based on its electroactive properties. This method can be highly sensitive but is typically used less frequently than other options. [33]

Each technique has unique strengths and weaknesses in terms of sensitivity, specificity, cost and throughput. LC-MS remains the most reliable approach for naproxen analysis in human plasma due to its high sensitivity and specificity, but the alternatives maybe chosen depending on analytical needs and equipment availability. LC-MS is commonly accepted by regulatory agencies (like FDA and EMA) for drug quantification in bio analytical studies because of its reliability. For clinical studies, LC-MS is typically considered as the 'gold standard' for ensuring data quality and reproducibility.

Process for analyzing naproxen in human using LC-MS technique

Analyzing naproxen in human plasma by LC-MS generally involves several steps:

1. Sample collection and preparation
2. Method development
3. LC-MS setup
4. Calibration, validation and analysis

Sample collection and storage: Collect the blood samples from participants and immediately process them to separate plasma by centrifuging the blood sample at 2000-3000 rpm for 10 minutes

Sample preparation: Naproxen is extracted from plasma using protein precipitation for liquid-liquid extraction process. Alternatively, for a cleaner extract, contaminants can be removed using solid phase extraction (SPE).

LC-MS method Development:

For Liquid chromatography (LC),

Column: Use a reverse – phase column, typically C18 for optimal separation. **Mobile phase:** A gradient or isocratic elution with mobile phases such as water with 0.1% formic acid (for aqueous

phase) and acetonitrile or methanol with 0.1% formic acid (for organic phase) is most common. The addition of formic acid helps to improve ionization and peak shape.

Flow Rate: Set an appropriate and acceptable flow rate based on column specification and technique sensitivity requirements.

For Mass Spectrometry (MS),

Ionization: Electrospray ionization (ESI) is commonly used in LC-MS analysis of Naproxen, as it generates charged molecules from the analyte in the solution.

Mass Analysis: In the mass spectrometer, naproxen ions are separated based on their mass-to-charge ratio. The MS is set to detect naproxen's specific m/z value, which is known and helps in identifying the compound.

Quantification: Multiple Reaction Monitoring (MRM) is a technique often used for quantification, where specific precursor product ion transitions are monitored, enhancing sensitivity and selectivity.[36]

CONCLUSION

Naproxen remains one of the most often used NSAIDs due to its effectiveness in treating pain, inflammation and fever across a number of conditions. An alternative HPLC method for quantifying naproxen in human plasma has been successfully studied. A simple and inexpensive liquid -liquid extraction process combined with an isocratic chromatography condition employing a reverse phase column results in an assay that is ideally suited for real time analysis. The analysis of Naproxen in human plasma using LC-MS with zidovudine as an internal standard is a reliable method for quantifying drug levels enabling for effective therapeutic monitoring, bioequivalence and pharmacokinetic investigations.

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